

“War spoke to us...”: cultural biographies of war memorials in Ukraine.

Abstract:

The paper explores the application of archaeological theory and methods to the study of contemporary conflict sites. It focuses on memorials created in the Kyiv region (Ukraine) after the full-scale Russian invasion in 2022, using a methodological framework that combines spatial analysis with cultural biographies of objects. This approach examines how war-affected objects and spaces are transformed and reused. The study identifies distinct patterns in the treatment of military and civilian objects and discusses how their original purpose and later memorialisation differ after experiencing violent events. Another key observation is the largely spontaneous nature of civilian memorials and their potential role in trauma integration. These findings show the need for further research into how both memorials and their perception evolve over time.

Keywords:

Russia-Ukraine War, spontaneous memorials, cultural biographies, conflict archaeology.

“...In painting such dark themes, pollution symbols are as necessary as the use of black in any depiction whatsoever. Therefore we find corruption enshrined in sacred places and times.” (Douglas 1984, 179-180).

Introduction

One of the challenges of studying any aspect of war while simultaneously living through it is that, over time, the materiality of war becomes commonplace and mundane for those experiencing it. War quickly becomes the new normal, so to speak. Archaeologists are especially accustomed to maintaining a temporal distance from the objects of their study. This allows us to observe the “processes” behind the things on a scale largely inaccessible to other social sciences. However, this comes at the cost of losing the voices of eyewitnesses and their perspectives on the things that surround them.

When our Department of Archaeology first contacted colleagues from the Centre for War Studies and Conflict Archaeology at the University of Glasgow, it was their external perspective that helped us view the ephemera of war through a researcher's lens. Duct tape covering windows, sandbag barricades, tanks repurposed as trash cans - war was altering the social and natural spaces in many details. These changes, in turn, transformed how we use and perceive those spaces, reshaping our usual routes and our imagination of what is garbage and what is precious.

I joined this project in spring 2024, having just completed my PhD thesis on Scythian barrows in the Azov Sea region, uncertain about what to do next, as the objects of my study had now become part of a battlefield. At first, the most important aspect of the project for me was documenting the transient materiality of war, at least its civilian side. Over time, I began finding more and more connections with my previous archaeological research. After all, kurhans are also memorials created by past communities to heal from loss and restore social bonds (Bradley 2024, 4; Inall 2020, 26). This led to the idea of approaching the study of war-related sites through archaeological methods that required no digging, only a reframing of how we view the spaces around us.

This topic is not completely unknown in archaeological and anthropological studies. Among other examples, Michael Rowlands in his paper “*Trauma, Memory and Memorials*” discusses the difference between monuments and war memorials (Rowlands 1998). The common aim of the latter

is to provide resolution for the living, transforming personal loss and memories into a social narrative of sacrifice that will not be forgotten. Rowlands' study focuses primarily on the 20th century, a time when the traumas of modern warfare demanded new approaches to commemoration. Modernist architectural perspectives emerged as a challenge to classical forms, rejecting their triumphalist narratives in favour of designs that strive for a kind of objectivity by confronting viewers with the stark reality of loss rather than subsuming it into idealised, heroic myths.

The ways memorialisation changes to overcome traumatic events become even clearer when looking further into the past. Liv Nilsson Stutz and Aaron Jonas Stutz examine archaeological perspectives on ritual responses that emerged after traumatic deaths and catastrophic events:

“We see not only ritual's great chronological depth, reaching back hundreds of thousands of years into our evolutionary past, but we also see how ritual may be deployed to handle anxiety over misfortune, may be weaponised to produce or exert political power, and may be adapted to cope or heal from crises.” (Nilsson Stutz & Stutz 2022, 39)

This dynamic is evident in the rituals of Minoan Crete following the catastrophic Santorini volcanic eruption in the second millennium BC. The collapse of Minoan society involved large-scale political and economic restructuring and subsequently significant changes in ritual practices. The shift from mountaintop sanctuaries to cave sanctuaries, the use of volcanic pumice in rituals and the emergence of individual burials with status symbols show how rituals were adapted to manage collective anxiety and reassert social order in the wake of disaster (Nilsson Stutz & Stutz 2022, 38–39).

Archaeology can offer a uniquely broad perspective on human actions, extending beyond our modern beliefs and power structures. Moreover, it has developed a particularly advanced methodology for studying material evidence and spatial relationships. While this expertise has primarily been applied to study the past, why not use this same methodological framework to gain insights into contemporary events?

One such approach that has gained particular traction in archaeology is the cultural biographies method. First introduced by Igor Kopytoff in his paper *“The Cultural Biography of Things: Commoditization as Process”* (Kopytoff 1986) and further developed by Nico Roymans (Roymans 1995), this approach suggests that certain events in the “life” of objects or places lead to transformations in their cultural meanings. Kopytoff refers to this process as singularization – a shift in an object's function by which it obtains a unique, non-exchangeable value. Applying this concept, the simultaneous discard and sacralisation of objects destroyed by war can be seen as a prime example of singularization, as *“to be a non-commodity is to be ‘priceless’ in the full possible sense of the term, ranging from the uniquely valuable to the uniquely worthless”* (Kopytoff 1986, 75).

Building on these frameworks I will address the question of how violent and destructive events in the “life” of things impacted their transformation into objects of commemoration. For this, I will analyze several memorials created after the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine. The field survey was conducted over a few weekends in June 2024, focusing on Kyiv and its surrounding areas. Parts of this region experienced temporary occupation by the Russian forces, during which local cities and villages became battlefields and were exposed to various violent events. Now, as they return to a relatively peaceful life, we can observe how the memorialisation of these events is depicted after they were reclaimed by Ukraine. Kyiv, on the other hand, was never occupied, yet it is particularly important as the political, geographical, and cultural centre of the country.

The sites selected for this study include memorials created from both military and civilian objects: vehicles, buildings, personal possessions. In the following sections, I will describe and compare the specific ways these elements are displayed and the spaces in which the memorials are located. The initial intentions behind their construction, the choice of location, and their subsequent treatment: all of this can help us better understand the materiality behind the violence and trauma caused by war.

Military equipment

Since the start of the war in 2014, memorials featuring military equipment, particularly destroyed vehicles, have become a common sight on the streets of Ukrainian cities and towns. While it is certain that most war remnants are being repurposed for military use, their symbolic power is no less significant. In this section, I will take a closer look at some of them and examine the general patterns discernable in the use of military equipment in creating war memorials.

Military equipment on Mykhailivska Square (Fig. 1). The street exhibition of Russian military vehicles, organised by the National Museum of Military History of Ukraine and the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine. This installation consists of nine vehicles and the details of the tactical missile system Tochka-U (NATO classification SS-21 Scarab). All of these are accessible to visitors, allowing direct interaction, and are covered with inscriptions: various profanities, condemnations of the enemy and glorification of the Ukrainian army. The condition of the objects is deliberately left deteriorated with shattered glass, corrosion, and bullet holes emphasising their role in warfare.

Destroyed Russian armored vehicles near Dmytrivka village (Fig. 2). The remnants of a Russian tank column, destroyed during the battles in the Kyiv region. Contrary to the previous example, these vehicles were left at their original location on the road leading to Kyiv. Several tanks lack armour components, possibly indicating their reuse in the initial months of the invasion. However, the only description board at the site has a warning to the civilians against any dismantlement. The surfaces of the majority of vehicles contain inscriptions made by visitors as well as occasional waste materials, like empty Cola bottles and used cigarettes. Although it partly functions as a war memorial, the distant location on the road makes it less accessible to the public.

“Veteran” car on Mykhailivska Square (Fig. 3). The exhibition of a Ukrainian military car, organised by the charity organisation MK Foundation¹. The car is covered with inscriptions from 54th Mechanized Brigade members. The description board details the locations on the frontline in the Donbass area where the car served for evacuation and support provision and includes a reminder that in war, the car is expendable.

Car on Kontraktova Square (Fig. 4). The exhibition of a Ukrainian military car, organised by the volunteer organisation “Enerhiia Serdets”². Despite displaying worn away features similar to those seen at Mykhailivska Square, this car has fewer inscriptions. The description board does not contain the details and story of this specific vehicle, focusing instead on a message to raise funds on cars for military intelligence.

Following the biographical approach, it is evident that it is not their destruction that transformed these vehicles or weapons into memorials. Instead, it was the change in context, particularly the spatial and functional context. A burned tank left on the battlefield is merely debris, but placed on the central square, it becomes a symbol.

A similar phenomenon, well-studied in archaeology, is the ritual sacrifice of weapons. One of the best-preserved Germanic sacrificial sites, Thorsberg Moor, active between the 2nd and 4th

¹ MK Foundation is a privately funded Ukrainian charity supporting the military, medical aid, and reconstruction (mkf.ua).

² БО "Енергія Сердце" is a non-profit organization in Kyiv that delivers humanitarian aid, including medical supplies, food, and drones, to support Ukrainian soldiers on the frontlines.

centuries AD, contained over 3,000 metal objects, particularly deliberately destroyed Roman *militaria*. Moreover, it is probable that the depositions were accompanied by public ceremonies which were performed at this location for several generations (Blankenfeldt, von Carnap-Bornheim 2018). Similar attitudes towards war loot can be traced in the Roman concept of *spolia*, a term specifically designated for the defeated enemy's armour and weapons. They were displayed before the community in temples and the most visible parts of houses (Katz 2014). Notably, it was considered sacrilegious to wear, use, or even repair them:

“They were regarded as peculiarly sacred, so that even if the house was sold the new possessor was not permitted to remove them...But while on the one hand it was unlawful to remove spoils, so it was forbidden to *replace* or *repair* them when they had fallen down or become decayed through age” (Ramsay 1875)

These weapons were withdrawn from their previous practical sphere of use and instead gained a new meaning as victory memorials.

The remnants of Russian equipment on Ukrainian streets can be considered as a classic example of such war trophies. They are typically displayed in central and highly visible parts of cities to symbolize victory and triumph. During the first Independence day since the full-scale invasion, on August 24, 2022, and after the Russian retreat from Northern Ukraine their tanks were exhibited on Khreshchatyk, the main Kyiv street. The deliberate choice of location was intended to subvert the Russian propaganda that had promised their victory parade on Khreshchatyk. Mykhailivska Square also holds significant symbolic value in modern Ukraine. During the Euromaidan³ events in 2013-2014, protesters found refuge from police troops in St. Michael's Golden-Domed Monastery, whose bells rang for the first time since the Mongol invasion in the 13th century, as claimed by its clergy⁴.

The message of the memorials featuring the damaged Ukrainian military vehicles may not be immediately obvious. How could it be appropriate to publicly display material evidence of military vulnerability in a country at war? The answer lies in the description of a "veteran" car: it stands as a testament to the daily struggles and sacrifices on the frontlines and of the responsibility of individuals to contribute to these efforts. The collective action and self-organisation of local communities played a crucial role in Ukraine's ability to withstand the first months of full-scale invasion, and now these destroyed cars remind people to maintain this spirit.

As we have observed, the Russian and Ukrainian equipment exhibitions have different purposes: the first is to raise morale, and the second is to promote ongoing community support. Despite their differing intentions, the way the objects are displayed and treated is remarkably similar. None of the vehicles have been repaired, as their destruction is the focal point of both messages. They feature similar inscriptions, mostly political statements. Some of them, like those at Mykhailivska Square, are even located side by side. One commonality among this weaponry is that it was all created for wartime use. Their destruction during war is intrinsic to their creation, making their eventual fate accepted as inevitable.

Civilian memorials

The occupation of Kyiv Oblast lasted a little over a month, but the devastation caused by it has left a lasting memory in the region. Hundreds of civilians were killed in war crimes, the most atrocious of which is now known as the Bucha Massacre⁵. More than two years later, the towns and cities still bear the scars of violence: walls of buildings are marked by artillery shelling, metal fences are bent, and holes in the asphalt remain. However, some of these remnants are now being

³ The Revolution of Dignity was a political movement in Ukraine that happened as a result of the suspension of the European Union association agreement by Viktor Yanukovich's government, escalating into mass protests demanding democratic reforms and European integration. <https://war.ukraine.ua/faq/revolution-of-dignity-ukraine/>

⁴ <https://euromaidanpress.com/2016/12/10/december-11-2013-the-bell-ringer-of-st-michaels/>

⁵ The Bucha Massacre refers to mass killings of civilians by Russian forces in Bucha, Ukraine, in March 2022 (<https://war.ukraine.ua/crimes/the-timeline-of-tragedy-bucha-massacre-nightmares-of-irpin-and-hostomel/>).

reimagined through art and sanctuaries, transforming sites of trauma into spaces of reflection and resilience.

Irpın “car graveyard” (Fig. 5). The collection of burned civilian cars near the Irpin city cemetery. It is located in a parking spot along the road through which their owners tried to leave the city under Russian shelling. Although not the only car collection point, this one received particular attention due to its proximity to both the city and the bridge over the Irpin River, one of the symbolic tragic sites of the events in winter-spring 2022. The cars show massive traces of artillery and fire damage. Inside them, one can still see the burned personal remains covered with shattered glass. Over time, however, the cars are gradually turning into art objects, with paintings of angels and sunflowers being the most prominent themes. Two years later, we observed children ride go-karts around this memorial showing how this place strangely embeds itself within civilian life (Fig. 6).

Flower paintings on fences in Bucha (Fig. 7). The several metal fences which were damaged by the mine explosion debris. The holes in the fences were painted over to resemble the centre of a flower bud.

Irpın bridge (Fig. 8). The remnants of Irpin bridge, blown by Ukrainian forces to stop the advancement of the Russian army towards Kyiv. Although a new bridge has since been constructed next to it, the old one has been left untouched since the time of the events. A spontaneous memorial has been set up under the bridge, likely in memory of the children who lost their lives during the shelling. The votive objects include stuffed toys, flowers, a broken baby carriage, and candles. Installations of paper angels and white storks have been placed on two bridge columns behind the memorial.

Burned power transformer (Fig. 9). Russian attacks on Ukraine's energy infrastructure have become another tool of terror. In the fall of 2024, a burned power transformer from one of the thermal power stations was displayed on Kontraktova Square, in front of a Kyiv-Mohyla Academy building. The transformer, visibly corroded and bearing traces of fire damage, became the centrepiece of an installation titled “*Where Is Your Light From*”. Yellow stripes on its side, each representing support for energy infrastructure workers, form the text of the title. On the asphalt surrounding the transformer, yellow lines resembling power circuits are drawn, along with inscriptions with the facts about the attacks. A nearby plaque recounts the biography of the transformer, named Orest. According to the description, Orest endured multiple attacks and survived, until the final strike caused damage so severe that restoration was no longer possible.

The impact of violence on the transformation of meanings is particularly evident in civilian sites. In the broader context, the most notorious examples of such places are industrial factories converted into battlefields (Azovstal) or torture camps (Izoliatsia). These impossible combinations are best described using the Foucauldian concept of *heterotopias*⁶, the real places with multiple paradoxical layers of meaning (Foucault 1984). There, the tragic events and the places themselves created the long-lasting link that consecrates and separates them from the rest of the environment.

The treatment of civilian material objects differs from that of damaged military equipment. Civilian memorials have no place for the enemy and rather portray the symbols of sadness and hope, loss and rebirth. However, the traces of destruction are not hidden, but instead reinterpreted to

⁶ This parallel was expressed by Olha Poliukhovich, particularly in her talk at the series of public discussions “Wartime Documentation: Literature, Memoirs, and Testimonies” on 22.04.2024 at the National University of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ELBQBsJ8QDU>

give these objects a new meaning. One can still observe the massive traces of fire on the cars in Irpin's "grave yard" and the flowers on Bucha fences not conceal but emphasize the bullet holes.

The events that happened play a central role in their current representation. But unlike arms and weapons, the violence and destruction that happened to these objects and places were not part of their intended purpose but stood in direct opposition to it. Therefore, their subsequent sacralization did not arise from just the loss of their practical function but rather from a traumatic event in their biography (Fig. 10).

Conclusions: Towards the archaeology of trauma response

In the final chapter of her anthropological work "Purity and Danger: An Analysis of Concepts of Pollution and Taboo" Mary Douglas discusses how societies embrace the negative aspects of life – such as pain, dirt, and death – through cult practices. While they may have strict taboos to avoid objects considered impure, these same objects can play a key role in rituals. Including these dark elements in the community narrative and social memory allows societies to face and accept reality in its fullness, thus restoring a shattered order. By engaging with these objects, people find a way to regain control over their lives and act rationally, as the alternative is madness (Douglas 1984, 160–180).

The archaeological record shows that communities engaging collectively in mourning and memory-making activities often used these practices as a foundation for maintaining social resilience. In their aforementioned paper, Nilsson Stutz and Stutz provide another example from the Great Plague, where the scale of mass death led urban centres to shift toward mass graves due to sanitary needs. In contrast, villages continued to perform traditional funerary rituals for much longer, even as the number of deaths grew (Nilsson Stutz & Stutz 2022, 35–36). The principle of providing a "good death" often remained non-negotiable during such crises. It could even be argued that the greater the crisis, the stronger the need to stage rituals, as they provide a culturally sanctioned framework for making sense of the trauma and violence.

While archaeology is, of course, silent on the question of people's responses and the mental health impact of memorials, modern anthropological and psychological studies provide insights into the specific needs these practices fulfill. A narrative meta-review on the therapeutic effects of spontaneous roadside memorials found that engaging in such activities can address needs no longer met by contemporary burial rituals (Arvanitis et. al 2020, 9). These practices offer individuals a sense of closure and create a space for belonging within a community that shares similar feelings. The memorials bring people together in grief and become a form of "solidified emotion of trauma" (Arvanitis et. al 2020, 11). However, the authors acknowledge that the sample size is limited so far, and more rigorous methodology is needed to draw definitive conclusions.

Many of the civilian memorials observed in this research were created spontaneously and have a grassroots nature. This shows one of the key advantages of conducting these surveys during an ongoing conflict: the ability to observe the memorials before they become part of an established political and historical narrative. At this stage, they remain genuine, authentic, and, at times, polarizing. While these examples are anecdotal, some acts, such as drawing flowers on damaged property, have sparked negative responses. These images could also be seen as disrespectful to the dead and as diminishing the gravity of events. Like in Douglas's study, we see that there is more than one way of embracing war and death pollution. But one thing is certain: it cannot be avoided by ignoring it, as the full-scale invasion has made obvious to any Ukrainian.

I was finishing this paper almost five months after the initial survey was conducted. Walking daily from the Academy on Kontraktova Square, up Andriivskyi Uzviz to Sofiivska Square and the Golden Gates, I noticed that the described sites were already changing. On Mykhailivska Square, military equipment now intertwines with parking spaces and is inscribed with the names of new cities and people. In the fundraising car on Kontraktova Square, a bouquet of flowers has been

placed inside. Meanwhile, new memorials, such as the power transformer installation, have appeared. The look and sound of the city keep evolving in response to new experiences, continuing to write an embodied commentary on this war.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Oleksandr Hanshyn and dr. Oleh Bilynskiy for guiding me through the war-related sites in the Kyiv region.

The project was supported by Documenting Ukraine, a program of the Institute for Human Sciences, IWM Vienna.

References

Arvanitis, K., Collins, H., Allsopp, K., Chitsabesan, P., & French, P. 2020. Psychological Impact of Spontaneous Memorials: A Narrative Review. *Psychological Trauma: Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/tra0000565>

Blankenfeldt, R. and von Carnap-Bornheim, C., 2017. Ritual sacrifices of military equipment in the Thorsberger Moor. In: M. Fernández-Götz and N. Roymans, eds. *Conflict Archaeology: Materialities of Collective Violence in Late Prehistoric and Early Historic Europe*. Themes in Contemporary Archaeology, Vol. 5. Abingdon/New York: Routledge, pp. 219–229.

Bradley, R. 2024. *Monumental Times. Pasts, Presents, and Futures in the Prehistoric Construction Projects of Northern and Western Europe*. Oxford: Oxbow Books.

Douglas, M., 1984. *Purity and Danger: An Analysis of Concepts of Pollution and Taboo*. ARK Edition. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul Ltd.

Foucault, M., 1984. Of other spaces: Utopias and heterotopias. [online] Available at: <https://foucault.info/documents/heterotopia/foucault.heteroTopia/en/> [Accessed 10 December 2024].

Inall, Y. 2020. A biography of memory: layered memorialisation of military death at an urban cenotaph. *Journal of the British Academy*, 8(s3), pp. 25-49. <https://doi.org/10.5871/jba/008s3.025>

Katz, R., 2014. Spoils. In: R.F. Thomas and J. Ziolkowski, eds. *The Virgil Encyclopedia*. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell

Kopytoff, I., 1986. The cultural biography of things: commoditization as process. In: A. Appadurai, ed. *The Social Life of Things: Commodities in Cultural Perspective*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 64–91. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511819582.004>

Nilsson Stutz, L., Stutz, A. J. 2022. Deeply human: Archaeological traces of rituals for coping with death, adversity, and trauma. In J. Gordon-Lennox (Ed.), *Coping rituals in fearful times: An unexplored resource for healing trauma*, pp. 23–42, Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-81534-9_2

Smith, W., 1875. *Spolia*. In: *A Dictionary of Greek and Roman Antiquities*. London: John Murray. [online] Penelope.uchicago.edu. Available at: https://penelope.uchicago.edu/Thayer/E/Roman/Texts/secondary/SMIGRA*/Spolia.html [Accessed 10 December 2024].

Rowlands, M. 1998. Trauma, memory and memorials. *British Journal of Psychotherapy*, 15 (1), pp. 54–64. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-0118.1998.tb00423.x>

Roymans, N. 1995. The cultural biography of urnfields and the long-term history of a mythical landscape, *Archaeological Dialogues*, 2 (1), pp. 2–24. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S138020380000026X>

List of figures.

Fig. 1. Military equipment on Mykhailivska Square.

Fig. 2. Destroyed equipment near Dmytrivka village.

Fig. 3. "Veteran" car on Mykhailivska Square.

Fig. 4. Car on Kontraktova Square.

Fig. 5. Irpin “car graveyard”.

Fig. 6. Go-karting at the “car graveyard”.

Fig. 7. Flower paintings on fences in Bucha.

Fig. 8. Irpin bridge.

Fig. 9. Burned power transformer.

Fig. 10. Biographical stages of military and civilian memorials.

